

Transform to Open Science (TOPS) at AMS 2023

Session Information

January 7-12

Title, Time, and Location	S	S	M	T	W	T
Student Conference - Table T20	✓	✓				
Colour of Weather + CHALA 7-9 PM - (Raices Brewery Co. 2060 W Colfax Ave. Denver, CO)		✓				
Transform to Open Science Presidential Session 10:45 AM - 12:00 PM - Mile High Ballroom 2B/3B (Ballroom Level)			✓			
OpenCore Workshops M/Th 1:30-4:00 PM T/W 9:00--11:30 AM Room 401			✓	✓	✓	✓
TOPS at the NASA Booth Exhibit Hall			✓	✓	✓	✓
TOPS Townhall 7:00 AM - 8:15 AM Mile High Ballroom 1EF				✓		
TOPS Mission Keynote 3:45 PM - 4:15 PM, Room 407					✓	
Open Science: DEIA 5-6:30 PM Hall A Exhibit Hall					✓	
Networking Reception (TBD)					✓	